

**Digital
Citizenship**

e-Presence and Communication Course

Readings | Exercises | Case studies | Quizzes

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Strategic partnership to develop open educational resources for teaching digital citizenship

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Introduction

The module “e-Presence and Communication” is very important. It deals with competencies related to online communication and interaction with others through virtual social spaces.

More and more people are spending a greater part of their lives online for many reasons that expand beyond work and entertainment. Maintaining an active online presence becomes increasingly important in terms of both work and personal life. Knowing how to communicate and address issues related to one’s virtual profile as well as image is among the top eSkill’s that people, especially young ones should master.

The Digital Citizenship Educational Handbook of the Council of Europe defines e-presence:

“... how you maintain your presence online and extends to your personal and interpersonal qualities that guide you in maintaining your digital reputation and digital identity. The extent and quality of your online presence can be found via a search online using your name or other personally identifiable information. Depending on the type of communications that you have engaged in, your e-presence can be negative or positive and, depending upon your social and cognitive skills for crafting your digital reputation, this can also boost or impede your e-presence.”

Likewise, communication within this context is defined as:

“... interactions, ideas, images, videos and pieces of information that you share and exchange with others through virtual social spaces. Obviously, communications can be offline as well as online, and online communications can spill over to offline and vice versa...”

Taken together e-presence and communication are effectively two parts that make a whole. One will affect the other and vice versa as based on the communication style you use your e-presence will be viewed in a certain light while how you aspire to be viewed will affect how you choose to communicate. This is very important as combining the two will amount to your online persona or avatar of sorts which is not always the same as your physical persona.

As such, the course will impart to participants those necessary skills to fulfil this competence. It will teach learners how to optimize their e-presence while Improving overall communication skills. It will further instruct learners on how to strategically approach e-presence and communication and imbue them with a sense of net morality while ensuring they can remain safe when employing their e-personas. However, the outputs of the course do not limit themselves to the digital world alone.

These skills have also many positive spillovers into their physical world. As such learners will be more apt to address real-life situations by being better able to respond and communicate their meaning. Furthermore, they will be able to perform related daily tasks more efficiently utilizing the best practices learned through this course and translating them into the physical world.

Using the knowledge obtained from this course, trainees will learn How to stay safer online and maximize their e-presence results by optimizing and using communication techniques and strategies.

All the modules follow the same style. This allows a buildup of familiarity for the learners. A Learner-centered pedagogy is adopted wherein Students use a combination of prior knowledge and new experiences to develop new skills that they apply to real-world examples and personal situations.

1. Module 1 - Introducing e-presence

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of e-presence as a general concept. It touches upon such issues as are what is e-presence, why it's important as well as exploring its effect on the physical world and vice versa. Students are guided to understand that having an e-presence is unavoidable.

Key Takeaways:

- Understanding e-presence
- Understanding the effects of e-presence in the physical world

What is e-presence

The term should be understood in the abstract as well as the specific. In the first instance, this means how in general the digital world views you and how you view yourself. An image gap is said to exist if the two do not align. However, this is something we will address later on.

Specifically, e-presence entails all online content related to you. This does not necessarily mean content only uploaded, posted and so on by you. It also means the content you follow, share, or are in any way part of. The digital footprint concept is what it's all about here. Under this notion, e-presence entails every possible link to you and ranges from something you yourself created and posted to even something that you simply viewed.

This is so as e-presence means different things to different digital citizens. Let's take two examples, that of your close friend and that of online marketers.

As to your friends, they will usually only concern themselves with things you posted and to a lesser extent with the content you shared. Your e-presence for them will be pretty much limited usually to just these. They will combine them with things they already know about you including both digital and physical interactions. Your e-presence then will be defined by a summarizing of these elements with your digital interactions with them weighing less than your physical ones.

For online marketers, however, a full analysis of your digital footprint will be required. They might look at what you posted and shared, but also the pages you visited and your duration of the visit there. They will also look at your recent purchases and expand this to your friends and your general social

circle. This happens because they wish to establish as much of an accurate image as possible about you as a consumer. This will help tailor their message and offerings to you.

Of course, this is done, with law-abiding marketers at least, in an anonymized manner. What this means is that an algorithm accesses data from all available sites connected to your account as per that account's privacy notice and cookies settings. This is why it's important to read the fine print in those user agreements. In any case, as said the process is anonymized and the software sends the same message and offers to people within a certain range of characteristics.

How does it differ from physical presence

The digital world is rather new to all of us. The internet itself in a very raw and unfamiliar to today's standards was only invented in the 1960s as opposed to the physical world, in terms of modern societies that have been around for more than a millennium. As such its rules and netiquette are still been formed and very few hard and universal standards have been set, as opposed to the physical world.

What this means is that, unlike established societies, the net society is still been formed. Things that were ok today might not be ok a month from now. This was observed with the introduction for example of various data protection regulations such as the GDPR of the European Union.

What this means is that physical societies took centuries to evolve. In doing so they had lots of time to adapt to their surroundings and form all those many norms inherent now in them. This could range from how you eat your food to when you should and if you should get married.

The Digital world however is still new. More than this it does not really limit itself within a geospatial location but truly encompasses the concept of globalization in its most extreme form. Digital citizenship is not limited to one country or locale within it and as such the prevailing culture is that of the world as a whole in a very rough aggregated sum. As such norms are much harder to establish and very easy to change.

Though you may know how to exist in the physical world you may lack the skills for the digital one. In essence, being a digital citizen with the associate e-presence means being a citizen of the digital world. Nothing remains constant here and meeting people with a different physical world culture is an everyday occurrence. Besides this and depending on the platforms, your e-presence, as opposed to your digital presence, perhaps might not be limited to one person or avatar.

How are e-presence and physical presence combined

The two, physical presence and digital presence are very much intertwined. Though different rules apply to these, as discussed above it could paradoxically be said that they are as similar as they are dissimilar and actions in the one can very well determine reactions in the other.

For example, advertisements you see online might result in a purchase in the physical world. The reverse is also true. Playing a video game online and adopting a certain character's behaviour pattern within the rules set for that game could result in character shifts in the real world. More than these concepts such as cyberbullying and trolling are coming to the spotlight in the physical world which returns with various campaigns limiting these behaviours and constantly providing guidelines to understand and address them.

It is well said that one's it's out there, it's out there. An embarrassing picture you or your friends uploaded decades ago could come back and haunt you. An upload such as a comment could be received the wrong way which could even result in you getting fired.

The digital world provides a sense of freedom, in being who you choose to be but this is not toll-free. You should always strive to have as much as possible identical digital twin and not vice versa. The reason for this is simple. The digital world is part of the physical world and not the reverse. At the end of the day, we live in the physical world whose rules and norms supersede those of the digital one and consequences will be much more severe in the physical one. Never underestimate the effect your digital persona can have on your physical persona and the world around you.

As such the topic will help learners understand these fundamentals. More than this it will help them realize that e-presence and physical presence go hand in hand together.

Why is e-presence Important

On average globally¹ people spend 2.12 hours every day on social media alone. For Europe, the average is slightly higher to 2.5 hours a day with some countries spending more and some less time online. The trend is for time spent online and in screen-related activities to increase in the foreseeable future.

As such, the digital world is becoming important and more so in the years to come. With it, who we are online and how we perceive this to be is becoming ever more crucial to our function in the physical world. Notice how we avoid using the term real world here.

This is so as the digital world has become as real as the physical world we occupy. These two as was said interact with each other struggling to find a working balance and both can affect not only the building and maintaining of the right kind of social relationships and balances with others that share this digital environment but also affect such things as employment, education, career, health, composure and in general every aspect of life.

For example, having the right kind of posts on your social media account could help you land a job. Most employers these days might spend an extra 5-10 minutes screening a potential candidate or keeping tabs on existing employees. Based on Career Builders² research, somewhere around 70% of employers do screen social media accounts of prospective employees while another 58% does so with existing employees. A 34% of those interviewed admitted to having even reprimanded or fired an employee based on content found in their online accounts.

This is but one example of how e-presence can have very real effects in the physical world. Friendships can be lost and personal traits altered as the boundaries between the two worlds come closer together to form a new concept of reality. Given this, it becomes essential to develop the right kind of e-presence skills to accompany your digital citizenship in this new and ever-changing environment to limit your exposure to the risk inherent in it.

¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/433871/daily-social-media-usage-worldwide/>

² <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/more-than-half-of-employers-have-found-content-on-social-media-that-caused-them-not-to-hire-a-candidate-according-to-recent-careerbuilder-survey-300694437.html>

Time spent watching TV or other media, playing computer games and similar screen activities outside work (hh:mm)

ec.europa.eu/eurostat

Case Study - What you say can and will be used against you

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Two UK teenagers were arrested and refused entry to the USA on suspicion of terrorist activity. A few days before travelling to the USA the pair posted on their social media account that they intended to destroy America. Upon arrival at the airport, the couple was detained in separate cells with Mexican drug dealers for 12 hours before being sent back to their country. It mattered little that the couple explained that the term destroy America was UK slang for excessive partying. The pair is now in the Homeland Security database.

Read the whole story here: <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2093796/Emily-Bunting-Leigh-Van-Bryan-UK-tourists-arrested-destroy-America-Twitter-jokes.html>

Self-reflection: Could you think about other types of posts that could affect you in the future? How could you be affected by those posts?

Why are e-presence skills important

Your e-presence skills are and will become determinative of your success in all areas. More and more people are joining the web and becoming increasingly involved in screen and online related activities. From existing and future friends to supervisors at work, prospective mates and online marketers all look to your social media for insides. As such who you are online and how you appear to be might not be the same to all and may have very real consequences on your physical life.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- Internet skills: the ability to use various apps and platforms correctly
- Media skills: the ability to understand that e-presence should be managed correctly
- Technical skills: the ability to understand that the internet and online services should be used in line with one's desired e-presence
- Safety skills: the ability to maintain a positive e-presence limiting exposure risk
- Confidence: the ability to truly match your physical and e-presence together
- Motivation: understanding why e-presence is important to all

Exercise 1: In the other's shoes

Objective:

- Understand why e-presence is important
- understand the permanent and unavoidable nature of e-presence
- Provide feedback

Duration: 15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper / forum, computer

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Try an online search of your name. Try different variations including popular social media and online platforms. You may be surprised at what you find

Tasks:

- Do an online search of your name
- Use different variations such as your name and various platforms
- Write down what you find.

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- Present it to your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates.

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes the fact that the digital world has a will of its own. Once the content is up there it is very hard to remove it

Lessons learned: e-presence is important and has a will of its own.

Forum

Objectives:

- Identify the e-presence of your role model or favourite person
- give feedback on whether their e-presence matches with what you had in mind

You may write down all the relevant material that you find.

Tasks:

- Search the net for the e-presence of your role model or favourite person such as an actor
- Write down if you encountered any surprises or not

Supplementary reading

10 People Who Were Arrested for Social Media Posts, Available at: <https://www.peepso.com/people-arrested-social-media-posts/>

2. Module 2 - Introducing communication

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of communication as a general concept. It touches upon such issues as what is communication, why it's important as well as the types of communication that exist. Students are guided to understand that improving communication skills is essential.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand what is verbal, nonverbal and written communication
- Discover the ways they are combined

Verbal communication

This is the first and foremost type of communication. It is one of the most essential skills anyone can possess and will determine to a large extent their ability to function in society.

Verbal communication can exist both in the physical world and in the digital world. This can be observed for example in either face to face discussions or through a web camera. If we limit verbal communication to just that, the exchanges of sounds that form words which in turn are connected to a specific meaning in our heads and transfer ideas as well as thoughts or general information then digital and non-digital verbal communication are largely indistinct.

To clarify, this limitation will include even such things as voice tone and colour. This is because things like this are more akin to non-verbal communication which we will examine later on.

In general, five types of verbal communication are said to exist. Included in the list are:

1. Intrapersonal Communication, meaning silent conversations we have with ourselves,
2. Interpersonal Communication, meaning private discussions we have with another on a one-to-one basis,
3. Small-Group Communication involves 3 or more participants but does not increase to a size where not everyone taking part in the discussion can interact with everyone
4. Large Group Communication involves 3 or more participants but does not increase to a size where not almost everyone taking part in the discussion can interact with everyone

5. Public Communication where interaction between senders and receivers of communication is rather limited

Each type of Verbal communication has of course its own set of skills. For Intrapersonal Communication, for example, self-reflection skills might be essential, for Interpersonal Communication active listening skills can be very effective and so on.

Nonverbal communication

Communication, in general, would be very hard without non-verbal communication. This type of communication was the first type of communication developed by our species.

Long before words had any meaning humans used unconscious expressions to convey meaning. We are not referring to signs and gestures or a form of sign language, this forms part of verbal communication. Instead, we refer to both universally understood micro expressions, facial gestures and body language that convey a general message or emotion. This could include for example facial expressions such as happiness or body gestures such as clapping your nose with your fingers at the smell of an intense odour.

In fact, according to Ray Birdwhistell, some ³ 70% of all communication is done so through non-verbal communication. In essence, these are clues that when used along verbal communication can help interpret the meaning as actually intended. Interestingly the first that was known for studying these cues was none other than Charles Darwin in his work titled *The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals* more than a century ago. Since then, the literature around the issue had grown. It is important to note that this is the only type of communication that can be understood to a large extent by people that do not speak the same language.

Among the many types of nonverbal communication that are accepted the main ones include⁴:

- First impression
- Posture
- Clothing
- Gestures
- Adapters
- Symbolisms
- Conversational
- Distance
- Chronemics

The list is long and many more could be added here. However, we keep it limited as we only intend to convey to you a general image of the area. However, what is important to understand here is that all these and many more are used consciously and unconsciously alongside verbal communication to help get our meaning across. As such studying these in ourselves and others cannot only help us to better convey our meaning but also receive the true meaning behind someone else's words.

³ Fontenot, Karen Anding (2018). "Nonverbal communication and social cognition". *Salem Press Encyclopedia of Health*.

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nonverbal_communication

Written communication

This form of communication is a direct product of our society. No other creature on earth is currently known to possess it at least not to such an exact form.

For example, though some animals use odour such as a dog marking its territory, these messages are too general to be able to transmit the amount and precision of information that can be transmitted through written communication employed by humans. By way of definition, we can say that written communication is the type of communication that uses assigned and specific symbols to convey meaning.

That being said, the invention of written communication was fundamental to our progress so far. Though verbal and non-verbal communication can and should be combined to convey meaning this written form of communication stands alone.

This is not to mean it does not get affected by them. Indeed, and especially with regard to the digital world, facial expressions and even images are used alongside written communication to help convey meaning such as emoticons and gifs.

In fact, written communication has long encompassed within it symbols that help the writer convey meaning such as question marks and exclamation points. Herein lies the paradox of written communication in that it can be viewed as a type of intrapersonal communication through interpersonal monologues.

For historians the importance of writing is unquestionable. History and prehistory are defined by the invention of writing. Everything in our lives has some form of written communication in it. From a package of gums to internet sites and entertainment, all would be rather difficult had written communication not come along. Of course, this too has advanced through the ages and a bundle of skills is involved in enabling the writer to achieve their goal.

Some of the most important ones involve:

- Research
- Outlining
- Editing
- Reading comprehension
- Time management
- Grammar
- Spelling
- Empathy
- Punctuation

Once more the list is long and non-exhaustive. There are tons of material out there and a number of professional courses to help you improve your writing skills. The key takeaway of this topic however is that writing skills really do matter.

Case study - It's written all over your face

A video from Paul Ekman on the nature of nonverbal communications. Professor Ekman was ranked 59th out of the 100 most cited psychologists of the twentieth century and his research on the biological relation of specific emotions demonstrated the universal nature of expressions.

Watch the video here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pVp5pGSwZkg>

Self-reflection: What kind of face would you put on for a job interview? What kind of emotions do you need to self-generate to bring you to the right state of mind? What would your face and body look like?

Why is communication important

The bedrock of our society is communication. No species on earth is without it and none has developed it to the extent we have. However, along with this specialization, a great burden is imposed. That is of developing the necessary skills to be able to communicate effectively with each other and this has applications in all walks of life. From simple social interactions to complex work relationships improving your communication skills is of paramount importance.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- Self-awareness skills: becoming more critical of ourselves and listening to our inner voice
- Media skills: the ability to effectively and accurately send and receive the information as it was meant to be sent or received
- Empowerment: The ability to better be able to understand ourselves and others
- Empathy: To be more in touch with other people's feelings and help ourselves and others to express these
- Conflict resolution: To be able to employ the best strategy depending on the situation and diffuse it
- Confidence: the ability to truly represent our thoughts and feelings and communicate accurately what we mean, while being able to decipher each other's meaning
- Motivation: understanding that communication skills are essential and investing in improving them is truly worth it

Exercise 2: Universal language

Objective:

- Understand that communication comes in many forms and shapes
- Provide feedback

Duration: 15 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper/forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: Write down what types of verbal, written and nonverbal communicators you think are universally understood or understood in the majority of countries. This can include anything from letters to expressions, hand gestures, body posture, chemical signals and so on.

Tasks:

- Write down forms of communicators you think can be universally understood.
- It could be anything
- Share it with your colleagues. While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. Teachers also add their own inputs

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes the fact that humans are one species so it is unavoidable that a lot of common communicators will exist among different cultures and languages. Understanding these can help us improve our communication skills.

Lessons learned: Common communicators exist and improving our skills means mastering these.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share any strange customs or norms you are aware of
- give feedback

You may write down any strange customs or norms you know of from any country and provide your input on why you think they came to be

Tasks:

- Write down any strange customs or norms
- Write down why you believe they exist or what purpose you think they serve

Supplementary reading

Smash Magazine, 50 Free Resources That Will Improve Your Writing Skills, Available at:

<https://www.smashingmagazine.com/2009/06/50-free-resources-that-will-improve-your-writing-skills/>

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3. Module 3 - e-presence and communication

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the connection between e-presence and communication. It touches upon such issues as how the two interact, why it's important to understand their relationship as well as exploring its effect on the physical world and each other. Students are guided to understand that e-presence and communication must be understood together.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand How e-presence and communication work together
- Discover how to combine them

Joining the two

Having a positive e-presence necessitates good communication skills. The overall image you wish to portray because this is what inevitably comes down to, requires the corresponding communication skills.

For example, journalists for the pop teen or high fashion magazines will need different skills. This is because even though the subject is the same, fashion, the audience and the expectations of the audience will differ greatly.

One must have a more fresh, younger feel to it while the other a more sophisticated outlook. The words chosen must be those of the audience intended and so the one might use more slang terms such as "peeps" while the other more classical terms such as "socialites" and where one might be freer to experiment with various colour combinations with respect to content and employ various emoticons the other will be more restrained taking an at least mild sophisticated outlook. The pictures of one might be those of a rave party they attended and the other of a dinner gala.

All these many little things blend in together to form your e-presence of choice. Anything used online conveys a message and is a type of communication that will affect your e-presence and as such must be aware of them. Even search terms and their combination are a type of communication as you let the algorithm of the search engine know what you are generally interested in. This in turn will be

computed alongside all your data made available to the algorithm, such as sites visited and duration of stay, to provide you with what it believes are the most suitable results for you.

As such the same search terms will produce different results for different people. Given that in the digital world everything you do conveys a message, you want to make sure it is the right one. Where a teenager posts a picture of herself in a bikini dancing with their boyfriend at a beach bar might be ok the same would not hold for the CEO of a multimillion-euro enterprise. The two whether we like it or not and despite any disagreements on the matter, are judged on very different standards.

So then before anything else you have to decide the type of e-presence you wish to have. This is your avatar. In general, one that wishes to have a positive e-presence when communicating should:

- Have in mind the concept of the digital footprint
- Always double check your message and think if it can be misunderstood
- Maintain privacy settings
- Avoid using public servers for sensitive information
- Adjust the message to the audience
- Think of the future
- Keep an appropriate tone
- Be respectful
- Embrace concepts such as free speech, access and inclusion
- Protect yourself and others from unwanted behaviours
- Take a proactive stance
- Remove unwarranted content such as spam and trolling
- Contribute positively to others' content as it is a win-win situation
- Learn to block, report and ignore malicious users

One cannot choose whether or not to have an e-presence. If you use the internet your digital footprint is there and this can have very real consequences for the world around you.

How does communication affect e-presence and vice versa

These two are unavoidably linked. In a strange paradox though communication in this broader sense described above will affect your e-presence the reverse is also true. Having the desired e-presence will lead to specific communication methods and these will revert back to that e-presence in a cause-and-effect manner that switches between the two. A pop star for example has the pop star image through the use of pop star-related communication methods and tools and these methods and tools lead to the pop star having that e-presence image.

Thus, both are equally based on each other. As such, managing your e-presence means adapting your communication skills to that e-presence you wish to implement. This is true even if you decide to be a digital hermit, meaning you limit your online exposure to the absolutely essential, such as emails or streaming online videos. Everything from choosing a name to the types of content you post should ideally align within at least the loose borders you wish to set.

For example, knowing how to set cookie notices can affect your e-presence in general. There are those who prefer more or less privacy and would or would not opt for tailor-made advertisements and content to be presented to them. This too is part of communication and the only way to transfer the right info to the server and algorithms tuning these is to understand the terms used. This is true not only for cookie notices but in many such similar things as privacy notices, terms of use, account options, security features and so on.

Here we need to add a small footnote. Through this, we discover another form of communication, beyond the aforementioned verbal, nonverbal and written types of communication. That of what essentially amounts to machine or digital communication. What this essentially means is that given most platforms are automated in their responses and only supported by real humans, one must be aware of the terminology they use and how in general they perceive information so as to be able to navigate them to their full extent.

Therefore, you must always keep both in mind. Discovering how you want your e-presence to be means also educating yourself on the broader concept of communication and understanding how the two interact so as to be able to follow the best alternatives.

Case study - Propaganda and public relations

A video explaining how communication in the sense of PR help change the world. The protagonist Edward Bernays is considered to be the father of PR and much has been attributed to him.

Watch the video here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V0OrT-8gXMs>

Self-reflection: Can businesses and politicians create new metaphors to manipulate public opinion?

Why are communication and e-presence important together

The two taken together translate to how we see ourselves and how the world sees us. When there is a difference between the two a gap is said to exist. Although you might want an online persona that is different from your actual character in the physical world it is still good to ensure that how you are viewed online is how you wish to be viewed online. This is the true meaning of the e-presence and communication gap.

Though the list is long some of the key competencies that need to be developed include:

- Communication and e-presence skills: Understand how the two relate to each other
- Self-awareness and reflection skills: the ability to truly estimate how you are viewed in the digital world

- Media skills: the ability to connect your actual e-presence to your desired one
- Empowerment: The ability to better be able to understand the importance of e-presence and communication as well as its ramifications
- Confidence: the ability to truly reflect your desired self onto others
- Motivation: understanding the importance of improving your communication and e-presence skills

Exercise 3: A masterplan in the works 1/3

Duration: 25 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper/forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: This task will be completed in three parts. In this first part, you are invited to draft your very own action plan with respect to your e-presence of your favourite social media as you wish it to be. Start by taking notes on how you wish others to perceive you. Answer why you think it is beneficial to be seen in that light whether it is for work purposes or socializing with peers. Then write down what techniques you think ought to be followed to achieve this. You should only use quick notes and bullet points

Tasks:

- Write down what your ideal e-presence should be based on your favourite social media. This will be your avatar. You can for example suggest that you wish to be an online comedian. Based on this you would then write down how others should perceive this persona
- Write down why you think is beneficial for others to view this avatar in the way you suggest
- Write down techniques to achieve this
- Share it with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. A teacher also adds their own inputs and draft their own plan

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes once more the importance of e-presence and communication. It explains to learners that designing your e-persona is not a random thing but takes careful planning to achieve.

Lessons learned: Both e-presence and communication should be followed in a strategic manner.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share different types of online personas that you like or dislike
- give feedback on why you think that is

You may write down any online personas you are a fan of or that don't like.

Tasks:

- Write down examples of online personas whether famous or infamous
- Write down why you think the appeal to people

Supplementary reading

10 TED talks to sharpen your communication skills: Available at:
<https://enterpriseproject.com/article/2018/6/10-ted-talks-sharpen-your-communication-skills>

4. Module 4 - Optimizing e-presence and communication

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with how to best go about improving your online presence. It touches upon such issues as best practices in the area, what is the difference between visual and non-visual presence as well as explores their effect on each other. Students are guided to understand that their e-presence should take a strategic direction by them.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand what is verbal, nonverbal and written communication
- Discover the ways they are combined

Best practices for optimizing e-presence and communication

Having understood e-presence and communication we can now see what we can do to optimize them. Moving forward we always keep in mind that the two affect and are affected by each other immensely.

Beyond this, we provide some useful tips on how to help maximize the effect of these two.

- Find your niche:

This means finding your place in the digital world. It means, simply put, discovering what and where you are good at and connecting this to an established community or creating your own. For example, if you are good at photography then look for online communities that share this passion or even consider creating your own. The Forbes⁵ 5 step guide could be useful in accomplishing this. The five steps require that you:

- 1) Evaluate your passions and skills
- 2) Figure out if there's a market for your niche
- 3) Narrow down your niche
- 4) Check out the competition for yourself
- 5) Test your niche

⁵ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/johnrampton/2017/11/07/a-5-step-formula-to-find-your-niche/>

What this means is that first you need to figure out what you're good at and passionate about. Then see if others share this interest. The more people that share this the bigger the market for it. Then you have to narrow down your niche by finding specialities within this market. From then on you need to check out the competition or your peers whatever the case may be to see what they are offering and how you can differentiate from them while absorbing as much knowledge as you can. The fifth step involves of course testing your niche by putting into action your chosen skill for the world to see and providing you with feedback.

- Identify problems you can offer solutions to

The world is full of problems and people pointing them out. What we desperately need and always need are those special few that can actually offer solutions to them. This should always be your goal, beyond pointing out a problem to offer your personal perspective on how this can be addressed. This will always help set you apart from everyone else.

- Be consistent

Maximizing your e-presence and communication involves a great deal of content to be created. Your audience however always needs training and will be creatures of habit as a norm. This means that they will function better with you if you operate within expected parameters. Meaning that if your interests and your chosen persona are one that focuses on theatre then content relating to online shopping could be out of place and might confuse their image or e-presence understanding of you.

This does not mean you cannot opt to be a jack of all trades. It just means that if you do you cannot really fixate on a single issue as those that first came to you with a specific understanding of your online persona are now presented with a completely different one which might lead them to search for somebody that still delivers what they originally expected.

- Be Timely

Set yourself a time schedule and keep deadlines as far as possible. For example, if you decide to 2 posts per week on specific days you need to try and keep that. Or if somebody asked you something or made a comment don't return an answer to them a month from then. This will help people understand that you are dependable and as such, they will more often than not approach you with whatever they have in mind.

- Be polite and professional

The world is full of time wasters. From trolling to Sunday drivers or Surfers in this case. Don't give in to your inner anger or feel offended by them; better learn how to ignore them or simply block them from contacting or seeing your content.

- Fact check everything

Before you share something make sure it's real. The digital world is full of content created for many purposes, from simply pranking to hacking and more and the last thing you want to do

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is help along with such content. For example, if you see a news story that you want to share you can first do an online quick search to see if it appears on incredible news channels. If it does not change is it is not a scoop but false news.

- Learn when and when not to use visual aids

For example, if you are writing a story you may need to enrich it by adding visual aids. If you are writing an email to your boss you may want to avoid that.

- Sometimes it's best to overcommunicate

Never assume that everyone understands your message. They could be politely noting along or responding with a simple ok or some other niceties. As such generally ensure that your message begins and ends with a summary of what you are trying to say.

- Be open and allow others to be open

Feedback is probably your most important ally. In order for this to work however you must truly be open to criticism so that people can tell exactly what is on their minds.

- Consider SEO

The acronym stands for Search Engine Optimization. In brief, given that this is a huge topic and a discipline of its own, the term stands for numerous techniques that can help your e-presence and contend be more discoverable by search engines and thus users. Fundamentals include using specific keywords and making your content relatable to those.

These are some of the most important things to have in mind in optimizing your e-presence and communication skills. As you journey through the digital world you will discover many more and assign your own important value to them.

Visual presence

Visual presence refers to the aesthetics your e-presence has. A picture is worth a thousand words and most people will make up their minds about you⁶ within the first minute of your encounter or even less.

As such visual impression and appearance do matter. Before even reaching the point of a person reading your content they will have a general idea about you. Whether they should or shouldn't is up for debate but what really matters is that most people do and you'll be dealing with most people.

This is true and indeed very broad. For example, if you are an online shop everything from the colours you chose to your logo, product arrangement, letter style, images displayed to the overall feel of your page will sum up to a first impression about your shop, which could be bad or good, even before the user reaches the part where they view your prices. When you deliver a document for review to your boss they will have already and to a large extent judged your work based on that overall impression they got, such as the title page, length, spacing, colours, graphs and overall tidiness.

⁶ <https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/how-many-seconds-to-a-first-impression>

So, it's good to make sure that this first minute works in your favour and not against you. In light of these, some things to keep in mind include:

- Keep it brief and to the point.

Most people are unable to escape that one-minute judgement. Their mind quickly looks to make sense of it all and you need to guide them there so as to make the right assessment. For example, if we are talking about a website make sure your landing page is made of colours that don't conflict or confuse, your logo is clearly visible and your welcome message is very short and explains exactly what you do. Pictures should be clean and in high resolution. On the other hand, if we are talking about work you submitted make sure that it has a first page with a title that really explained what the work is about and you have used letter styles that your boss is familiar with. A relevant picture might also help depending on what the work is about and if that is accustomed or not in your specific profession. Where in lawyers this would be odd in advertisers this would be expected.

- Keep it engaging

Visual aids are key here. Whether a graph or a relevant picture all visual aids can encourage the user to continue occupying themselves with your content.

- Don't be misleading

Your visual no matter how appealing needs to connect to your substance. Otherwise, you will lose credibility and if that happens things will get tough for you. For example, if you're running a story about an online sale about to happen don't use pictures from crowds of people pushing and shoving each other to get to your products accompanied by a title riots are expected to come. Though many people will click on it and some will also find it funny and perhaps be engaged most will view this as clickbait and will not bother with you anymore.

- Keep it neat

Try avoiding the temptation of including too many things. Sometimes in an effort to become appealing, we load content with tons of visual aids. These rather than inviting the audience could simply overwhelm them and confuse them

- Use high-quality visual content

Better to use a high-quality visual aid or none at all. A poor-quality video for example will have the opposite effects as it will tend to bring down all other content. People expect consistency and usually think in terms of black and white. Something is either good or not.

- Keep your audience in mind

Whether an online job interview or a social media post you should keep it relevant. If the interview is for a barista job then jeans and a shirt would be most suitable. If it is for a new CEO Position, then a suit and Tie area must be.

All of the above are good to be kept in mind. However, when thinking about your visual presence always remember that this is part of the equation and not the complete solution. At the end of the day, people will want to reach your actual content and this should not be outweighed by your visual.

Non-visual presence

The non-visual presence relates to your actual message. Reminding you that once more we talk about e-presence and communication as an interrelated concept, everything that has to do with this relates willingly or unwillingly to a message.

This will be the substance of your communication. Getting past the first impression, now it's your chance to either confirm that positive image or correct the negative one. Not all great relationships start with love at first sight and there is plenty you can do to help yourself.

A lot of these have been already covered. For example, you can develop further your self-reflection skills. That way you will know more about exactly what it is you offering and what message you want to convey. You can enhance your non-verbal communication skills. This will allow you to better read the responses of people, especially to that first image and correct or confirm as necessary. You can improve your SEO skills and a general understanding of online platforms to improve your machine communication skills. You can practice your writing skills to make sure your message is conveyed clearly while enhancing your active listening skills so as to enable yourself to better respond to the actual message being sent while improving your audience engagement.

Most of all you have to truly understand what nonvisual presence is about. On the surface of it, this topic involves your content in and of its own. However, if we wish to go deeper, we will realize it is a form of unconscious presence. It is for example the reputation we have even before we have reached a person directly. This could be for example the word of mouth about us or a ranking we have on our favourite movie critic platform.

It also involves another element. How the automated digital world perceives us, how these algorithms that communicate on 0's and 1's read our presence. Whether that is they read it at all and if they categorise it as wanted or unwanted. For example, when your email ends up in the spam folder those 0's and 1's need a good talking to. The same is true if your search engine results present you on the fifth or sixth page.

As such Non-visual presence must be approached carefully. It must be done from both the conscious and the unconscious aspects of it. It must also appropriately be combined with visual presence.

Case study - 10 well-known miscommunication instances

Miscommunication is defined as a social inability to communicate adequately and properly. It could affect the person who communicates, the information receiver, a group of people or even the entire world. Watch a short video on 10 well-known miscommunication instances here:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aSRDWcEm1GA>

Self-reflection: What do you do to make sure that you are well understood by family, friends or even overseas buddies?

Why should you optimize e-presence and communication

As it was said, your e-presence can have a mind of its own. You have to then make sure that you guide it towards the path you want it to take and be proactive in how it goes about presenting you to the digital world by ensuring your e-presence and communication skills are and stay as sharp as ever.

Though the list is long some of the key competence that needs to be developed include:

- E-presence and communication awareness: Ensuring you understand the connection between the two
- Netiquette: The proper way to behave online
- Awareness: To know what your true e-presence is
- empowerment: To be able to guide your e-presence where you want it to go
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content and optimize their positive effects
- Confidence: the ability to more effectively use the net
- Motivation: understanding the importance of strategically using communication skills to improve your e-presence and in general your approach to things

Exercise 4: A masterplan in the works 2/3

Duration: 25 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper/forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: This task will be completed in three parts. In this second part, you are invited to apply the best practices you learned and improve your very own action plan with respect to your e-presence with respect to your favourite social media as you wish it to be. Share aspects that you wish to communicate with the class and write down which of the themes covered you think are most useful to incorporate in your plan.

Tasks:

- Finalize your plan
- Write down which of the things covered in this module you found most useful and which you have trouble with. Share these with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. The teacher also adds their own inputs and finalizes their plan

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes once more the importance of e-presence and communication. It explains to learners that designing your e-persona is not a random thing but takes careful planning to achieve.

Lessons learned: Both e-presence and communication should be followed in a strategic manner.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share different types of miscommunication you know of
- These could be personal or well-known ones

You may write down any instance of miscommunication you are aware of.

Tasks:

- Write down instances of miscommunication
- Provide feedback

Supplementary reading

Taking a different aspect below you will find tips on improving workplace communications, <https://axerosolutions.com/blogs/timeisenhauer/pulse/210/41-smart-tips-to-improve-communication-in-the-workplace>

5. Module 5 - E-presence and communication safety

Snapshot

Summary: This topic deals with the fundamentals of e-presence and communication safety in general. It touches upon such issues as how to stay moral and avoid improper behaviours online, as well as exploit the kind of remedies one can avail to themselves or others. Students are guided to understand that knowledge is essential to these.

Key Takeaways:

- Understand how to stay safe and protect others
- Discover the ways you can do this

Staying ethical online

Truly the digital world is a much freer place than the physical one. There is in most cases very little scrutiny with respect to how we behave online while anonymity and pseudonyms are all too common.

With these the temptation to behave unlike we would in the physical world is great. However, it is the lack of immediate ramifications to our person that determines our quality and as such, it is that much more important to maintain our ethics when we are online. Though precise guidelines cannot really be set, as the digital world is ever expanding in concepts and content, still some basic fundamentals ought to be observed.

According to Paul Wallbank, A senior technology Consultant expert These ⁷include:

- Private stays private
- Don't misquote
- Never plagiarize
- Give credit where possible
- Be open about affiliations
- Resist anonymity
- Be polite
- Don't go overboard

⁷ <http://paulwallbank.com/2010/12/08/online-ethics/>

Though it is up to each one of us to serve our online ethics we can all agree on these fundamentals. In general, we should all try to observe those universal values commonly accepted as the right things to do in the physical world and even perhaps take it a step further by being extra careful when we enter the digital world. This is so as unlike the physical world we cannot really see or hear the people behind that screen usually.

As such it is hard to assess their composure. To know their sensitivities or if they begin to take insult in things we say. If we were in the physical world, nonverbal communication would have stepped to the rescue. Yet as this is impossible to do in the digital world, with some exceptions as are online meetings using cameras, it is a good idea to keep in mind that our skills of empathy are limited there and so an extra effort should be put into helping them along.

Digital good manners

This section largely overlaps with the previous one. The distinction can indeed be thin and perhaps it would be best to consider digital good manners as going the extra mile from staying ethical online.

For example, failing to say thank you to someone who provided a comment is not immoral. But it would be polite to do so as would ending each email with a thank you or kind regards depending on the case. Following the same reasoning as before of not adopting hard and fast rules, there are some minimum standards, we can all agree on. However, it should be noted that as there are cultural norms that might appear strange to those of other cultures so is the case with the digital world. Like the physical world though to a smaller extent societies within the digital one have their own norms.

In any case, the most fundamental good manners include:

- Acknowledge the other's interest in our content
- Avoiding using the digital world when we are in the presence of a company
- Abiding by the rules of each group and instructing new members about them
- Mentoring newcomers
- Maintain the same level of respect as we wish to be given
- Keep a positive and truthful tone
- Ensure that your message cannot be misunderstood by doublechecking it
- When you mention someone as far as possible let them know they are being mentioned
- Broaden your perspective by not taking things too seriously when you shouldn't

As we said this area overlaps significantly with the previous one. The distinction would be one we have to make and more of a judgment call approach is needed here. All will depend on the situation at hand and its many variables which cannot be predicted. In essence and even more than what we do with staying ethical online more vigilance is needed on our part to maintain digital good manners that could perhaps be summarized in the do unto others as you want others to do to you.

Recourses to unethical and improper behaviour

Though the digital world provides certain impunity it is not without any remedies. In fact, most digital environments within the digital world such as platforms and selling sites will have some form of defence against improper behaviours.

Most social media sites for example will have a way for you to block someone. This could be an effective solution that's quick and easy to implement. They will also have a report option and a category this falls into. For example, it could be unsolicited sales that qualify as spam or harassment,

hate speech, phishing, trolling, explicit content and so on. The admins of the social media will then examine this post you reported and will decide the appropriate sanctions to impose.

These could be numerous and range from a denial of services to a complete block. Given that a lot of social media and internet apps are owned by the same companies the effect on this person could be severe as the ban could extend to a number of other apps and platforms. As such and because the IP address is tracked in these instances the consequences on the perpetrator could indeed be very serious. You can see for example a relevant Forbes article⁸ on what ransomware is.

This brings us to another point. Make sure you read at least once the rules and terms of use of the platform. That will be your best weapon as it will generally outline the grievance procedure to follow. Beyond this and for Europe at least the GDPR guarantees a minimum set of rights at least with regard to your personal information. Most platforms abide by this and ensure that they assign competent officers to address any concerns or requests you may have.

Case Study: Cyberbullying in America

Beyond the EU, many countries are taking strong steps to address the issue of cyberbullying and empower people against it. Watch a short video on Cyberbullying in America here:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bW_Dg4588E

Self-reflection: What does prosecutable mean to you?

Why is e-presence and communication safety important

Both the physical world and the digital world can be very productive environments. However, just like the physical world is full of risks so is the digital one. It is thus important not only to learn how to keep ourselves safe but also how to protect others from online improper behaviours.

Learning this will also teach us how to avoid hurting others. Though we may have the best intentions sometimes, because of the way the digital world works we could accidentally hurt someone by our acts or omissions. From sharing fake news without clarifying that we don't believe in the story or we're sharing it just for fun to sending a message that can be misunderstood staying ethical online and having the proper netiquette is becoming increasingly important.

From trolls to scammers the list of those that would take advantage is long. To this, you should arm yourself with the necessary knowledge and skills to combat these.

⁸ <https://www.forbes.com/sites/tjmccue/2020/12/31/yikes-here-is-what-happens-when-you-respond-to-spam-emails-plus-five-tips/>

Though the list is long some of the key competencies that need to be developed include:

- Self-awareness skills: the ability to know more of the consequences of our actions
- Media skills: the ability to navigate various forms and tools of online content with a willingness to correct wrongs we see as well as to avoid causing unintentional harm to others.
- Empowerment: the ability to help ourselves and help others to protect themselves from improper online behaviours
- Digital ethics and good manners; The ability to be a moral digital citizen
- Empathy: To be more in touch with other people's feelings and how content can affect them
- Confidence: the ability to stand up for your rights and others
- Motivation: understanding that safety is important

Exercise 5: A masterplan in the works 3/3

Duration: 25 minutes

Tools: pen, piece of paper/forum

Methods: classroom discussions, description, comparison,

Description of the exercise: This task will be completed in three parts. In this third part, you are invited to apply the safety precautions you have learned and improve your very own action plan with respect to your e-presence of your favourite social media as you wish it to be. Share aspects that you wish to communicate with the class and write down which of the themes covered you think are most useful to incorporate in your plan.

Tasks:

- Add safety precautions to your plan
- Write down which of the things covered in this module you found most useful and which you have trouble with. Share these with your colleagues.
- While you present your list, the teacher will consolidate it with all answers given by your classmates. The teacher also adds their own inputs and add them to their plan

Debriefing: The trainer emphasizes once more the importance of e-presence and communication safety. They explain to learners that they must be careful not to cause harm to themselves and others.

Lessons learned: That e-presence and communication safety are important aspects.

Forum

Objectives:

- Share different types of unethical or improper behaviour you know of
- These could be personal or well-known cases

You may write down any instance of unethical or improper behaviour you are aware of.

Tasks:

- Write down instances of unethical or improper behaviour
- Provide feedback

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Supplementary reading

Consumer rights in the EU

A page with many links on consumer protection in the European Union that can be very useful:
https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/consumer-rights-and-complaints_en

6. Assessment quizzes

Module 1

- 1) What is ePresence in the abstract sense?
 - a) How in general the digital world views me and how I view myself
 - b) How I behave online
 - c) How people act online

- 2) What is ePresence in the specific sense?
 - a) How in general the digital world views me and how I view myself
 - b) All online content related to you
 - c) How to stay moral online

- 3) On global average, how much time is spent on social media every day by an individual?
 - a) 2.12 hours
 - b) 1.2 hours
 - c) 11 hours

- 4) Why is ePresence important?
 - a) It is not
 - b) Because the digital and physical worlds are intertwined
 - c) It's only important if you want to get a job

Module 2

- 1) What is verbal communication?
 - a) Giving of commands to the computer
 - b) Messages transmitted orally through the use of words and speech
 - c) Messages transmitted through social media texts

- 2) What is nonverbal communication?
 - a) Messages transmitted through various nonverbal or written stimuli and signals
 - b) Messages transmitted orally through the use of words and speech
 - c) Messages transmitted through written text

- 3) What is written communication?
 - a) Messages transmitted orally through the use of words and speech
 - b) Voice commands
 - c) Messages transmitted through written text

- 4) How are verbal, nonverbal and written communication linked?
 - a) All start from verbal communication
 - b) They affect each other in numerous ways and hence influence our presence online
 - c) They are not

Module 3

- 1) What is the most important thing in having a successful ePresence?
 - a) A great personality
 - b) Good communication skills
 - c) Advertisement

- 2) Are the needs for online communications skills different from person to person?
 - a) All the people have the same communication needs
 - b) Yes, it depends on your goal
 - c) Some people may need different skills but most do not

- 3) How do Communication and ePresence relate?
 - a) One shapes the other
 - b) They do not
 - c) Communication decides ePresence

- 4) Various algorithms cannot affect your ePresence:
 - a) Yes, these are just for people to pass their time pleasantly
 - b) Based on your previous content interactions, algorithms decide which content is made available
 - c) Only to a small extent

Module 4

- 1) Visual and non-visual presence:

- a) Are the same
 - b) Complement each other
 - c) Have no relation to each other
- 2) Find your niche means:
- a) Gaining money
 - b) Finding where you are good at and an audience that likes it
 - c) Becoming famous
- 3) Which of the below would make your ePresence meaningful?
- a) Pointing out problems you already believe you have an answer to
 - b) Pointing out problems
 - c) Pointing out what does not work
- 4) Being consistent means:
- a) Always wanting to maximize your ePresence
 - b) Following a communication strategy that is the same through your interactions
 - c) Posting always the same thing

Module 5

- 1) Staying ethical online:
- a) Is not something you should care about
 - b) Is something very important with a lot of consequences in the real and digital world
 - c) Does not affect the real world
- 2) Digital good manners involve:
- a) Only saying thank you
 - b) Some etiquettes depending on the situation
 - c) The same thing as real-world good manners etiquettes
- 3) Whatever you do online:
- a) Can very much affect the real world
 - b) Stays online
 - c) Has a small effect on the real world

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- 4) If someone misbehaves online:
- a) There is nothing you can do
 - b) Most online environments provide you with solutions
 - c) You should not care about these types of people

7. References

- APS, 2006, How Many Seconds to a First Impression?, available at:
<https://www.psychologicalscience.org/observer/how-many-seconds-to-a-first-impression>
- Axero, 2015, 41 Smart Tips to Improve Communication in the Workplace, available at:
<https://axerosolutions.com/blogs/timeisenhauer/pulse/210/41-smart-tips-to-improve-communication-in-the-workplace>
- Consumer rights and complaints, 2021, Europa, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/consumer-rights-and-complaints_en
- Council of Europe, 20019, Digital Citizenship Education Handbook
- Career Builder, 2019, More Than Half of Employers Have Found Content on Social Media That Caused Them NOT to Hire a Candidate, According to Recent CareerBuilder Survey, available at: <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/more-than-half-of-employers-have-found-content-on-social-media-that-caused-them-not-to-hire-a-candidate-according-to-recent-careerbuilder-survey-300694437.html>
- Daily mail. 2012, 'I'm going to destroy America and dig up Marilyn Monroe': British pair arrested in U.S. on terror charges over Twitter jokes, available at:
<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-2093796/Emily-Bunting-Leigh-Van-Bryan-UK-tourists-arrested-destroy-America-Twitter-jokes.html>
- Edward Bernays: on Propaganda and Public Relations, available at: Here:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V0OrT-8gXMs>
- Eurostat, 2015, Are Europeans glued to their screens?, available at:
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/DDN-20180507-1>
- Fontenot, Karen Anding (2018). "Nonverbal communication and social cognition". *Salem Press Encyclopedia of Health*.
- Forbes, 2019, Yikes! Here Is What Happens When You Respond to Spam Emails, Plus Five Tips, available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/tjmccue/2020/12/31/yikes-here-is-what-happens-when-you-respond-to-spam-emails-plus-five-tips/>
- Keith Deltano, 2020, Cyberbullying Video for Schools (Lessons / Education) for Middle School and High School Students, available at:https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bW__Dg4588E
- Paul Ekman, 2013, Outsmart Evolution and Master Your Emotions, available at:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pVp5pGSwZkg>
- Paul Wallbank, 2010, Online ethics, available at: <http://paulwallbank.com/2010/12/08/online-ethics/>
- Peepso, 2015, 10 People Who Were Arrested for Social Media Posts, available at:
<https://www.peepso.com/people-arrested-social-media-posts/>
- Statista, 2019, Daily time spent on social networking by internet users worldwide from 2012 to 2019, available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/433871/daily-social-media-usage-worldwide/>
- Smash Magazine, 50 Free Resources That Will Improve Your Writing Skills, available at:
<https://www.smashingmagazine.com/2009/06/50-free-resources-that-will-improve-your-writing-skills/>

The enterprisers project, 2018, 10 TED talks to sharpen your communication skills, available at:
<https://enterpriseproject.com/article/2018/6/10-ted-talks-sharpen-your-communication-skills>

TopTenzNet, 2015, Top 10 Times Miscommunication Had Awful Consequences, available at:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aSRDWcEm1GA>

Wikipedia, 2021, Nonverbal communication, available at:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nonverbal_communication

Appendix

Assessment quiz check sheets

Evaluation quiz Module 1 check sheet – correct answers

1a

2b

3a

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 2 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2a

3c

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 3 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2b

3a

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 4 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2b

3a

4b

Evaluation quiz Module 5 check sheet – correct answers

1b

2c

3a

4b

Instructional design review checklist for youth workers

No	Criteria	Yes	No
1. Objectives			
1.1	Are objectives stated clearly for the learner?		
1.2	Are the course requirements consistent with the objectives?		
1.3	Do chapters/topics thoroughly cover the course's objectives?		
1.4	Do the learning objectives match the learning outcomes?		
1.5	Does the overall content and structure of the course meet its instructional objectives?		
2. Structure			
2.1	Does the course have a concise and comprehensive overview or syllabus?		
2.2	Does the course include examples, analogies, case studies, simulations, graphical representations, and interactive questions?		
2.3	Does the course structure use appropriate methods and procedures to measure student mastery?		
3. Content			
3.1	Does the content flow seamlessly, without grammatical, syntactical and typing errors?		
3.2	Is the content up-to-date?		
3.3	Is the content aligned with the curriculum?		
3.4	Are the desirable outcomes incorporated into the content?		
3.5	Is the content in compliance with copyright laws and all its quoted material cited correctly?		
3.6	Does the course engage students in critical and abstract thinking?		
3.7	Does the course have prerequisites or require a technical background?		
4. Assessment			
4.1	Are the assignments relevant, efficient and engage students in a variety of performance types and activities?		
4.2	Are practice and assessment questions interactive?		
4.3	Do the practice and assessment tasks focus on the course's objectives?		
5. Technology - Design			
5.1	Is the design clear and consistent, with appropriate directions?		
5.2	Are the images and graphics of high quality and suitable for the course?		
5.3	Is the course easy to navigate and offers assistance with technical and course management?		
5.4	Is the course navigation structure consistent and reliable?		
5.5	Are the course hardware and software defined?		
5.6	Are the audio and on-screen text in sync?		
5.7	Does the architecture of the course allow instructors to add content, activities and extra assessments?		

Feedback on topic for students

Assessment of Module						
Course title:	Privacy and Security					
Module Title:	Introducing privacy					
Part A:	On a scale of 1-5 where 1 is the lowest and 5 the highest level of agreement indicate how you feel on the following					
	Observations	1	2	3	4	5
1	The subject was interesting					
2	I believe the topics covered were important					
3	I would like to know more about the area					
4	I have learned new things which I am likely to apply in the future					
5	I would like to improve my skills in the area					
6	I am likely to recommend this course					
Part B:	In the space provided please feel free to include any comments and recommendations you wish to make					
Part C:	In the space provided please feel free to include your email address if you would like to be kept informed about this project					

